

2nd version

VISUAL GUIDE

How to utilize NodeXL importers
and further functionalities

FREE GUIDE

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July 2025

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NODEXL

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VISUAL GUIDE

How to utilize NodeXL Importers
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01

NodeXL Importers

"X" (Twitter) Importer 3.0

Learn more [here](#)

1

Options > Import > Upload the recipe

Recipe

2

Data > Import > From X (formerly Twitter) Search Network 3.0 (beta)

Import

From X (formerly Twitter) Search Network 3.0 (beta)

3

Type your query > Adjust other parameters of interest > OK > Authorize NodeXL to use your account

Type your query

If required, adjust Start Date / End Date / Limit of tweets

If you're unable to download your data, try deleting the token and logging in again.

4

In just a few minutes, you'll get the network along with the metadata!

Instagram Importer

Learn more [here](#)

1

Options > Import > Upload the recipe

2

Data > Import > From instagram network (beta)

Import

From Instagram network (beta)

3

Type your query > Adjust other parameters of interest > OK > Authorize NodeXL to use your instagram account

Type your query

Adjust parameters

If you're unable to download your data, try deleting the token and logging in again.

4

In just a few minutes, you'll get the network along with the metadata!

BlueSky Importer (beta)

Learn more [here](#)

1

Options > Import > Upload the recipe

Recipe

2

Data > Import > BlueSky Search Network (beta)

Import

From BlueSky Search Network (beta)

3

Type your query > Adjust other parameters of interest > OK > Authorize NodeXL to use your account

Type your query

Adjust your parameters

For new queries reauthenticate

4

In just a few minutes, you'll get the network along with the metadata!

1 Options > Import > Upload the recipe

Recipe

2 Data > Import > From Flickr Tags Network

3

Get your API and type your Query

Execute the Query

4

5

In just a few minutes, you'll get the network along with the metadata!

Reddit Importer

Learn more [here](#)

1

Options > Import > upload the recipe

2

Data > Import > From Reddit Search Network (beta)

3

Authorize NodeXL to use your account > type the Query > Adjust other parameters of interest > OK

4

In just a few minutes, you'll get the network along with the metadata!

YouTube Importer

Learn more [here](#)

1

Options > Import > upload the recipe

2

Data > Import > From YouTube Video Network

3

Type your Query in a search word option or enter IDs for particular videos > adjust other necessary parameters

4

Data you obtain:
Title, description, tags, author, creation date (UTC), views, comments, like count, dislike count and a link to the video.

Explore your results

Learn about YouTube User Network importer [here](#)

By Dr. Verónica Espinoza (2025)

Wikipedia Importer

Learn more [here](#)

1

Options > Import > upload the recipe

2

Data > Import > From MediaWiki Page Network

3

Open a Wikipedia page of your interest > type the information as shown in the image.

Explore your results

4

You can adjust additional parameters, such as the number of reviews, network depth level, date range, and more.

WhatsApp Importer

Learn more [here](#)

1

Options > Import > upload the recipe

2

Data > Import > From WhatsApp (beta)

3

Import your file > Adjust parameters of interest > OK

4

Explore your results

Importers:

- Brandwatch
- Meltwater
- Talkwalker
- TweetBinder

“

NodeXL team has implemented importers for data sets created by Brandwatch, Meltwater, Talkwalker and TweetBinder.

”

Learn more [here](#)

1

Data > Import > select the importer of your interest

2

Apply a recipe > explore your results

Import data from Brandwatch

Learn
more
[here](#)

1

Data > Import >
From Brandwatch (Beta)

2

Upload your
BrandWatch .xlsx file

3

Options > Import >
upload the recipe

Import this recipe

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1qb7C0su6jwg2e9n3wxxwikKKL_kFqO/view?usp=sharing

4

Graph > Automate
> Run

5

In just a few minutes,
you'll get the network
along with the metadata!

Import data from Talkwalker

Learn more [here](#)

1 Open your Talkwalker data and locate the **source_type** column.

2 Filter only the Twitter data from Talkwalker in Excel, then either copy and paste it into a new file or remove the other sources in the same file.

3 Data > Import > From Talkwalker (Beta)

4 Upload your Talkwalker .xlsx file

5 Options > Import > upload the recipe

Import this recipe

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1gb7C0Su6Jjwo2e9n3wvwwkKk1_KFcQ/view?usp=sharing

6 Graph > Automate > Run

7 In just a few minutes, you'll get the network along with the metadata!

02

Networks from other sources

1

Download the CSV data from the PubMed website.

2

Option 1: co-occurrences
Turn a list of items (per row) into a network of items:

Clement, Marie, Bruno, Azeem, Lucy
Clement, Vincent
Vincent, Jaime, Garance

import this table to get this network

Option 2: sources and targets
Turn a list of sources and their targets into a network of sources based on how many "targets" they share

Students ("sources")	Courses taken ("targets")
Vincent	marketing, finance, strategy
Jaime	marketing, linguistics, branding
Lucy	modern literature, linguistics, semantics
Louise	modern literature, linguistics, phonetics

import this table to get this network

Prepare your data with the NocodeFunction Tool, using the available options to create networks based on co-occurrences or lists. You can also use the Table2Net Tool to prepare your data.

3

Import the network file into NodeXL > apply a recipe > Explore your results

From Kaggle [website](#), download a dataset that aligns with your interests.

2

Prepare your data with the NocodeFunction [Tool](#), using the available options to **create networks based on co-occurrences or lists**. You can also use the [Table2Net Tool](#) to prepare your data.

3

Import the network file into NodeXL for visualization > apply a recipe > Explore your results

Interview Transcript Data

Full
tutorial
here

1

Transcribe the interview

2

Prepare data with the NocodeFunction Tool using the option turn your text into semantic graphs.

3

Import the network file into NodeXL > apply a recipe > Explore your results

03

More possibilities

NodeXL Metrics Report

Make a Dashboard in one click!

Full tutorial [here](#)

A tool developed by me

This app processes data from the "Vertices" tab of your NodeXL template to generate a metrics report, helping you analyze and understand your network data more effectively

A tool developed by me

Launch my tool here: [tool](#)

NodeXL Data + Python = Graphistry

Full tutorial [here](#)

Visualize your NodeXL Data in Graphistry using Python

1

NODEXL GRAPH GALLERY

The screenshot shows the NodeXL Graph Gallery website. The main area displays a list of graphs with their respective logos and social media links. A red arrow points from this interface to the Python code block. The sidebar on the left contains various navigation options, with a yellow circle highlighting the 'Download the Graph Data as a NodeXL Workbook' link.

2

```
# pip install -q --user graphistry

pip install -q --user openpyxl

import pandas as pd
import graphistry
graphistry.__version__

# To specify Graphistry account & server, use:
graphistry.register(api=3, username='...', password='...', protocol='https', server='hub.graphistry.com')

#g = NodeXLGraphistry().xls(xls, 'twitter')
g = graphistry.nodexl('https://www.nodexlgraphgallery.org/Pages/Workbook.ashx?graphID=286794')

print('%s nodes, %s edges' % (len(g._nodes), len(g._edges)))
g._nodes.sample(2)

g.plot()
```


g GRAPHISTRY

NODEXL

3

Geolocated Tweets

GENERAL FORMULA FOR GEOLOCATING IN X
geocode:lat,long,radius (km/mi)

1

The initial step is to find the necessary data in Bing Maps: **latitude, longitude, and radius** of the specific region we aim to target in our search.

2

Enter your query along with the geolocation data including latitude, longitude and radius from Bing Maps. Follow the general formula to geolocate your Tweets.

NodeXL Pro INSIGHTS

NodeXL Pro INSIGHTS is a Microsoft Power BI report template that allows the creation of interactive network reports from NodeXL Pro Twitter datasets.

NodeXL Graph Gallery

Learn
more
here

NodeXL Graph Gallery it is a website where community has published more than 80,000 network maps on a vast variety of topics from various data sources.

The network reports in the gallery summarize the most important information created with a NodeXL workbook which include top influencer, hashtags, URLs, words, word pairs and more.

Two Methods to Create a Semantic Network

Method 1: From a NodeXL Text Column

STEP 1

Click on **“Graph Metrics”**

The screenshot shows the NodeXL 'Graph Metrics' dialog box. In the top right, a red box with a '1' points to the 'Graph Metrics' button in the main menu. In the middle left, a red box with a '2' points to the 'Words and word pairs' option in the 'Metrics to calculate and insert into the workbook' list. In the middle right, a red box with a '3' points to the 'Tweet' dropdown menu in the 'Word and Word Pair Metrics' sub-dialog. In the bottom center, a red box with a '4' points to the 'Calculate Metrics' button. Another red box with a '3' points to the 'Positive' sentiment list in the 'Sentiment Analysis' section of the sub-dialog.

Select **“Words and word pairs”**

Select the column that contains the text of which you want to make the semantic map (from Vertex or Edges)

Calculate Metrics

Method 1: From a NodeXL Text Column (continued)

Learn more here

- From the previous step, you will obtain this information.
- This information will be used to create the semantic map.
- We will name it: **TEMPLATE WITH ORIGINAL DATA**

	A	B	C	DE	F
1	Word 1	Word 2	Count	Group	Word1 on Ser
2	#web3	#cx	1240	(Entire gr	
3	#insurtech	#nodexl	1235	(Entire gr	
4	#ehealth	#finserv	1228	(Entire gr	
5	#healthtec	#smartcity	1228	(Entire gr	
6	#digitalhe	#web3	1228	(Entire gr	
7	#frenchtec	#chidambar	1228	(Entire gr	
8	#nodexl	#traveltec	1228	(Entire gr	
9	#cx	#ehealth	1228	(Entire gr	
10	#mwc23	#insurtech	1226	(Entire gr	
11	#chidambar	#bigdata	1222	(Entire gr	
12	#datascler	#csuite	1221	(Entire gr	
13	#csuite	#digitalhe	1221	(Entire gr	
14	#vive2023	#healthtec	1220	(Entire gr	
15	#iiot	#mwc23	1220	(Entire gr	
16	#traveltec	#ai	1220	(Entire gr	
17	#finserv	#iiot	1220	(Entire gr	
18	#ai	#frenchtec	1220	(Entire gr	
19	#bigdata	#selfdrivin	1220	(Entire gr	
20	#smartcity	#5g	1219	(Entire gr	
21	#5g	#datascler	1219	(Entire gr	

Words and Count

Word Pairs and Count

STEP 2

- Open a new NodeXL template and perform the listed actions.
- This template will be used to visualize your semantic map.
- We will name it: **NEW TEMPLATE FOR SEMANTIC MAP.**

Import Semantic Network – count recipe

In **EDGES** tab, rename this column by "Count"

In **VERTEX** tab, also rename this column by "Count"

Acciones de documentos

NOXO Pro

A PROJECT OF THE socialmedia RESEARCH FOUNDATION

NodeXL Pro is updated frequently. Here are the most recent changes

- Fixed bug for Wiki User-User (Discussion) networks
- Added a "Date" and "Time" column for Twitter networks
- Added separate "Edge Weight" column for each "Relationship" type in Edges when exporting to GEXF

New step-by-step tutorials on network analysis with NodeXL Pro:

- Social network and content analysis with Twitter network data [pdf]
- How to Automate NodeXL Pro [pdf] [video]
- Semantic Networks – Create networks with words, hashtags or video tags

Method 1: From a NodeXL Text Column (continued)

Learn more here

STEP 3

Prepare the data as shown below.

TEMPLATE WITH ORIGINAL DATA					NEW TEMPLATE FOR SEMANTIC NETWORK				
Word 1	Word 2	Count	Group	Word1 on Sentiment List #1: List	Vertex 1	Vertex 2	Reciprocated	Count	Other Columns
#webs	#cx	1240	(Entire gr	FALSO	#webs	#cx		1240	
#insurtech	#nodexl	1235	(Entire gr	FALSO	#insurtech	#nodexl		1235	
#health	#inserv	1228	(Entire gr	FALSO	#health	#inserv		1228	
#healthtec	#smartcity	1228	(Entire gr	FALSO	#healthtec	#smartcity		1228	
#digitalhea	#web3	1228	(Entire gr	FALSO	#digitalhea	#web3		1228	
#frenchtec	#chidambar	1228	(Entire gr	FALSO	#frenchtec	#chidambar		1228	
#nodexl	#traveltecl	1228	(Entire gr	FALSO	#nodexl	#traveltecl		1228	
#cx	#health	1228	(Entire gr	FALSO	#cx	#health		1228	
#mwvc23	#insurtech	1226	(Entire gr	FALSO	#mwvc23	#insurtech		1226	
#chidambar	#bigdata	1222	(Entire gr	FALSO	#chidambar	#bigdata		1222	
#datascier	#csuite	1221	(Entire gr	FALSO	#datascier	#csuite		1221	
#csuite	#digitalhea	1221	(Entire gr	FALSO	#csuite	#digitalhea		1221	
#vive2023	#healthtec	1220	(Entire gr	FALSO	#vive2023	#healthtec		1220	
#liot	#mwvc23	1220	(Entire gr	FALSO	#liot	#mwvc23		1220	
#traveltecl	#ai	1220	(Entire gr	FALSO	#traveltecl	#ai		1220	
#inserv	#liot	1220	(Entire gr	FALSO	#inserv	#liot		1220	
#ai	#frenchtec	1220	(Entire gr	FALSO	#ai	#frenchtec		1220	
#bigdata	#selfdrivingca	1220	(Entire gr	FALSO	#bigdata	#selfdrivingca		1220	
#smartcity	#5g	1219	(Entire gr	FALSO	#smartcity	#5g		1219	
#5g	#datascier	1219	(Entire gr	FALSO	#5g	#datascier		1219	

TEMPLATE WITH ORIGINAL DATA					NEW TEMPLATE FOR SEMANTIC NETWORK				
Word	Count	Group	Word on Sentiment	Word on Sentiment	Vertex	Vertex Pair Ratio	Count	Other Columns	
#nodexl	1474	(Entire gr	FALSO		#nodexl		1474		
#chidambar	1466	(Entire gr	FALSO		#chidambar		1466		
#ai	1360	(Entire gr	FALSO		#ai		1360		
#digitalhealth	1333	(Entire gr	FALSO		#digitalhealth		1333		
#web3	1314	(Entire gr	FALSO		#web3		1314		
#5g	1309	(Entire gr	FALSO		#5g		1309		
#bigdata	1301	(Entire gr	FALSO		#bigdata		1301		
#mwvc23	1296	(Entire gr	FALSO		#mwvc23		1296		
#health	1294	(Entire gr	FALSO		#health		1294		
#vive2023	1286	(Entire gr	FALSO		#vive2023		1286		
#healthtec	1286	(Entire gr	FALSO		#healthtec		1286		
#cx	1271	(Entire gr	FALSO		#cx		1271		
#liot	1267	(Entire gr	FALSO		#liot		1267		
#selfdrivingca	1264	(Entire gr	FALSO		#selfdrivingca		1264		
#smartcity	1263	(Entire gr	FALSO		#smartcity		1263		
#enilev	1262	(Entire gr	FALSO		#enilev		1262		
#mwvc2023	1251	(Entire gr	FALSO		#mwvc2023		1251		
#csuite	1246	(Entire gr	FALSO		#csuite		1246		
#datascientist	1240	(Entire gr	FALSO		#datascientist		1240		
#socialmedia	1237	(Entire gr	FALSO		#socialmedia		1237		
#insurtech	1232	(Entire gr	FALSO		#insurtech		1232		

STEP 4

Run the recipe in your **NEW TEMPLATE FOR SEMANTIC NETWORK**

STEP 5

You will now obtain your semantic network! You can explore it using the **Zoom** and **Scale** functions. You can also save it by pressing **Ctrl+I**.

Demo

Method 2: Using NodeXL Semantic File Generator

Learn
more
here

A tool developed by me

Step 1

Copy the "Word 1", "Word 2", and "Count" columns from your NodeXL template (excluding headers) and paste them into the App

Word 1	Word 2	Count
dua	lipa	363
propio	póster	292
previouslyfilmx	#barbiemovie	279
mejor	pelicula	278
pelicula	mejor	276
margot	robbie	271
#barbiemovie	atención	265
#barbie	#barbiemovie	265
póster	#barbiemovie	189
oficialmente	'barbie'	176
lipa	oficialmente	176
'barbie'	propio	176
barbie_context	dua	173
ryan	gosling	165
#barbie	mejor	138
mejor	mejor	138
manera	#barbie	138
mejor	mundo	138
arturourbanos	manera	137
rahhh	manera	137

Step 2

Process and download to GEXF file

⌚ Wait for the App to load

NodeXL Semantic File Generator

by Dr. Verónica Espinoza

www.nethabitus.org [Twitter @Verukita1](https://twitter.com/Verukita1)

- 1.- Copy the "Word 1", "Word 2", and "Count" columns from your NodeXL template (excluding headers) and paste them into the app.
- 2.- Click "Download GEXF File" to generate the file.
- 3.- Import the file into NodeXL and run the corresponding recipe to visualize the semantic network.

Step 3

Import and visualize in NodeXL your GEXF file generated in the App and apply the recipe that I share with you.

Download the recipe [here](#)

Launch my tool here: [tool](#)

[Demo](#)

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Connect with me

2025

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Resources

[Download the full set of NodeXL Pro data recipes](#)

[Meet NodeXL-Pro: one tool, many possibilities!](#)

[Mapping Twitter Topic Networks: From Polarized Crowds to Community Clusters](#)

[Connect to Networks with NodeXL: The official guide](#)

[Analyzing Social Media Networks with NodeXL: Insights from a Connected World. 2nd edition](#)

[Articles regarding NodeXL by Dr. Wasim Ahmed.](#)

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